

Design of Power SiC Transistor Embedded in PCB Supported by 3D Thermo-Mechanical Simulations

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This study presents a thermo-mechanical simulation of a power SiC transistor integrated into a printed circuit board (PCB). The primary objective is to optimize the design to enhance the thermal and mechanical properties of the device. Through numerical simulations, critical areas within systems utilizing power transistors embedded in PCBs are identified and optimized to reduce mechanical strain and improve heat dissipation. These improvements contribute to the overall reliability of the final system.

1. Introduction

The newly developed technology of embedding dies in printed circuit boards (PCBs) eliminates the need for wire bonds by using direct metal contacts or soldering instead. This advancement reduces parasitic inductance, capacitance, and resistance associated with wire bonds, thereby enhancing the electrical performance of a device. Additionally, the embedded packaging enables double-sided cooling for a power component [1, 2]. Mechanical stress created by a thermal expansion is very important key factor for the reliability and long lifetime operation of a power device. During the development process of new technology, numerical simulation is a powerful tool for design and optimization [3].

This paper details a thermo-mechanical simulation analysis of a power SiC transistor integrated within a PCB. Analyses demonstrate various thermal and mechanical stress behaviour and properties at different geometry designs and operating conditions.

2. Structure and model description

The focus of this investigation is on SiC power MOSFET transistor embedded within a PCB. As illustrated in Fig. 1, 3D model shows the MOSFET SiC die mounted onto a copper lead frame. This configuration is integrated into a double-sided PCB made of FR4 material. Lamination and plating techniques are employed to establish two additional copper routing layers on both the top and bottom surfaces of the PCB. These layers are connected via vias, which create the drain, source, and gate contacts. The simulation utilized thermal and mechanical properties sourced from the standard COMSOL library [4]. The heat source was placed on top of the SiC power transistor die, where heat is generated during operating conditions.

Fig. 1 3D model of embedded power SiC MOSFET for thermo-mechanical simulations.

3. Simulation results

The analysis of embedded power MOSFET focuses on how the geometry of specific layers affects thermal and mechanical stress properties and behaviour. Variables examined include via diameter, via thickness, via spacing, and lead frame size.

First, the impact of the investigated variables on the thermal properties is analyzed. Fig. 2 shows the time-dependent simulation of the thermal impedance Z_{th} for the embedded device. The device's temperature varies directly with the thermal impedance, meaning that as the thermal impedance increases, so does the device's temperature. The higher thermal impedance means higher device temperature. From the simulations, higher via diameter and lead frame size decrease the device thermal impedance mainly at times from 1×10^{-1} s up to steady state due to higher thermal conductivity of the heat sink from SiC die through the higher area. The higher via distance slightly increases the thermal impedance in the range around time 1×10^{-3} s. The higher via distance leads to a lower thermal capacity of the vias. The impact of via thickness on thermal impedance is almost negligible.

After thermal analysis of the device, the mechanical stress induced by thermal expansion was examined. The mechanical stress was assessed at three different times: 1×10^{-3} s, 1×10^{-1} s, and the steady-state operating condition (DC). The analysis focused on the vias, where potential failure could occur. Fig. 3 illustrates the mechanical von Mises stress in the vias for varying via diameters, via thicknesses, via distances, and lead frame sizes.

Fig. 2 Simulated thermal impedance Z_{th} of the device at different investigated geometry variables.

Fig. 3 Mechanical stress in the vias at different investigated geometry variables for various pulse times.

Although the thermal impedance and the associated device temperature are marginally lower with larger via diameters, the mechanical stress increases due to the more robust and less flexible nature of these larger vias. On the other hand, despite the slightly elevated

thermal impedance and temperature with increased via thickness at a pulse time of 1×10^{-1} s and in steady state, the mechanical stress is more evenly distributed within the vias, leading to a reduction in stress. The distance between vias does not impact mechanical stress at 1×10^{-1} s and in steady state conditions. However, when the vias distance increases, the mechanical stress slightly increases at 1×10^{-3} s. This increase is directly proportional to the changes in thermal impedance and temperature around 1×10^{-3} s. Furthermore, a substantial reduction in thermal impedance and temperature with a larger lead frame size decreases the mechanical stress in the vias at 1×10^{-1} s and steady state conditions.

4. Conclusions

Presented thermo-mechanical simulation study of a SiC power transistor embedded in a PCB demonstrates a substantial influence of geometric design on the thermal and mechanical stresses experienced by the embedded power transistor. The results highlight how specific design parameters critically affect the overall performance and reliability of the device. It shows that mainly higher lead frame size leads to lower device temperature and mechanical stresses. Since the mechanical stress in the device layers and interfaces proportionally degrades the device reliability, lower mechanical stress prolongs lifetime at a steady state and especially during cycling, pulse operating conditions.

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